

Research Paper

Application of artificial neural networks for characterizing the hydrodynamic performance of oscillating water column devices

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ABSTRACT

This work investigates the application of artificial neural networks to improve the characterization and assist in the optimization process of oscillating water column wave energy converters, thus increasing the reliability and accuracy of performance predictions. More specifically, this work addresses the challenges associated with resource-intensive physical modelling by combining neural networks with specifically designed experimental campaigns, thereby reducing the dependency on exhaustive experimental testing while maintaining predictive accuracy. The methodology integrates multilayer perceptron networks with Levenberg-Marquardt training, selected for their robustness and suitability for regression tasks. Key parameters, including significant wave height, energy period, and turbine-induced damping, are used as inputs to predict accurate performance in terms of capture-width ratio. Among the tested configurations, a network with a single hidden layer of 20 neurons demonstrated the best balance between accuracy and generalization, achieving a root mean square error below 2.5% and a correlation coefficient very close to unity ($R > 0.99$) when validated against experimental data. The selected neural network model is subsequently applied to analyse the performance of an oscillating water column device operating at a case study site, accurately predicting its capture-width ratio matrix for untested turbine-induced damping values and enabling the identification of the optimum damping through a parametric search. The findings confirm that artificial neural network based frameworks are a valuable tool that can provide information which streamline the design and help the optimization process of oscillating water column devices.

1. Introduction

The exploration and utilization of renewable energy resources are essential for addressing the global energy demand while mitigating climate change [1]. In particular, wave energy represents a promising and largely untapped source of clean energy [2] with enormous potential. Among all the available technologies for capturing the motion of ocean waves to generate electricity [3], oscillating water column (OWC) wave energy converters (WECs) are among the most widely studied devices. OWCs utilize the oscillatory motion of waves to alternatively compress and decompress the air inside a chamber, which then drives a turbine to produce electricity. Although the simplicity of an OWC device—consisting primarily of a hollow chamber and an air turbine—is one of its main advantages, accurately characterizing and optimizing its performance remains a significant challenge. In particular, the efficiency of an OWC system depends largely on the characteristics and interaction of these two elements, the turbine and the chamber. The turbine must

operate effectively under the bidirectional airflow conditions generated by the oscillations of the water column. To deal with this situation, self-rectifying impulse turbines are the most widely employed solution [4]. Among them, impulse turbines, such as the biradial turbine, have emerged as some of the most promising turbine technologies due to their high efficiency and robust performance under a wide operating flow range [5]. Regarding the chamber, its geometry must be designed to achieve resonant conditions under the most energetic sea states at the intended coastal deployment site. Several studies have investigated the optimization of OWC chamber geometries (e.g., [6–8]). In this context, constructal design provides a physics-based framework for systematically improving OWC performance [9]. The Constructal Law states that finite-size flow systems evolve toward configurations that facilitate easier access to the currents flowing through them [10]. When applied to OWCs, this approach allows the geometric parameters of the chamber to evolve under prescribed constraints in order to enhance air flow, pressure oscillations, and ultimately the wave-to-air energy conversion

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efficiency [11]. Although constructal design provides a systematic framework for improving OWC performance through geometric optimization, the effectiveness of this approach depends on a thorough understanding of the complex physical processes governing the device operation.

The performance of an OWC is strongly affected by non-linear processes involved, such as the air compressibility [12] or other complex interactions, as the turbine-chamber coupling [13], which significantly influence the system performance. In particular, the damping induced by the turbine on the oscillations of the water column is one of the key parameters affecting the efficiency of an OWC device [14,15]. Consequently, comprehensive and advanced modelling is essential for the further development and optimization of this technology [16], particularly in the case of novel OWC concepts and design innovations, which increasingly include complex three-dimensional geometries [17]. Among recent innovations, energy-concentrating OWCs [18,19], permeable load-reducing OWCs [20,21], and multi-chamber frequency-broadening OWCs [22,23] have attracted considerable research interest. These studies have effectively addressed major challenges associated with OWC devices, such as low energy capture efficiency, poor survivability, and a narrow effective frequency bandwidth. Nevertheless, they have also led to increased complexity of OWC systems, making it difficult for traditional numerical methods to analyse these devices with satisfactory accuracy and computational efficiency.

While both numerical and physical models can be used for this purpose, physical models remain essential for reliably evaluating the performance of the device when subject to wave action, avoiding the inherent simplifications that numerical models imply, even with the most advanced computational fluid dynamics (CFD) models [24] or wave-to-wire models [25,26], proper validation against experimental measurements is essential to ensure accuracy. However, physical modelling methods involve extensive wave flume or wave tank testing [27], and therefore demand considerable economic and human resources. In the light of these limitations, the development of more efficient tools to reduce the dependency on physical tests emerges as a key aspect for accelerating the development of WECs, and more specifically, OWCs.

Artificial intelligence (AI) has been largely used since the 1990 s, usually divided into machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) [28,29]. These subfields focus on creating algorithms and models that can learn and make predictions based on data [30]. These methods have been proven to be extremely effective in a wide range of applications, such as natural language processing, computer vision or time series analysis [31,32].

In this context, artificial neural networks (ANNs) have emerged as a valuable alternative to conventional modelling approaches [33,34]. ANNs are computational models capable of learning complex relationships within data, making them suitable for multiple applications [35], from forecast predictions [36,37], wave downscaling [38], selection of suitable locations based on available resource [39,40] or even the creation of artificial models [41], as a matter of this work, interpolating datasets derived from OWC experiments. By effectively learning the underlying patterns in test results, ANNs can minimize the need for exhaustive experimental campaigns while maintaining the accuracy of performance predictions.

OWC devices have been studied through ANNs for several purposes. By training them using a database of inputs and outputs, ANNs can predict the optimum geometric parameters that improve energy conversion efficiency. In particular, studies have been conducted to optimize the chamber design of OWC devices, both for converters with conventional-shaped chamber [42] and for U-shaped or L-shaped configurations [43]. Other studies have explored the optimal design of an inclined barrier set up in front of the device for performance improvement [44]. Additional applications of ANNs in OWC systems include enhancing turbine rotational speed control of OWC systems [45] and estimating the air pressure within the chamber based on turbine

rotational speed and water level [46]. Closely related to the present study, López and Iglesias [33] developed a virtual laboratory that enables the determination of the capture-width ratio of an OWC under given wave conditions through an ANN. However, this study primarily focused on regular waves tests and neglected the effects of air compressibility. These limitations were addressed in subsequent works [27], although only at the experimental model level, providing a baseline for the present study.

The primary objective of the present research, and its novel contribution, is to integrate the use of ANNs to accurately characterize the performance of OWC devices with different configurations operating under realistic conditions, thereby reducing the reliance on physical modelling [47]. Realistic conditions involve considering the entire wave climate—represented by different irregular wave conditions—at a site of interest and avoiding common simplifications, such as disregarding viscous effects or the spring-like effect of air compressibility, both of which are known to influence the performance of real devices. To accomplish this goal, firstly, the study expands the physical testing campaign presented in [27], to develop an extensive dataset for training and validating the ANN models. Second, a systematic evaluation of different ANN architectures is conducted to identify the optimum ANN architecture for providing accurate and consistent predictions, validating the ANN results against the experimental dataset. After validation, the ANN model is used to predict the OWC performance for specific significant wave height and wave energy period combinations, and for a given turbine-induced damping value (i.e., a turbine of a specific diameter). Finally, the resulting ANN is used to determine the damping value that maximizes the efficiency of the OWC converter. The findings demonstrate the potential of ANNs to reduce costs associated with experimental testing while offering precise insights into device behaviour, fostering the development and deployment of OWC systems.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Artificial neural networks

An ANN is a brain-inspired computational model made up of interconnected processing units, or neurons, that learn patterns from data [48]. They typically consist of three interconnected layers—input, hidden, and output—through which data flows sequentially (Fig. 1). The input layer collects and forwards data for processing. The hidden layer processes this information through weighted connections, making use of activation functions (e.g., *ReLU*, *sigmoid*, *tansig*) to capture nonlinear relationships [49]. Finally, the output layer generates the final prediction [50]. Learning occurs via forward propagation of the inputs through the network to compute outputs (predictions) and backpropagation, in

Fig. 1. General functioning scheme of an ANN.

which errors are calculated and used to update network parameters using optimization algorithms [51].

For the present study, a multilayer perceptron feedforward neural network (MLP) was implemented due to its suitability for regression tasks [52,53]. Training was conducted using the Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm (LMA), which adaptively combines the gradient descent (first-order) and the Gauss-Newton (second-order) methods to achieve both rapid convergence and robust stability [54].

The determination of the optimum ANN architecture (i.e., the number of hidden layers and the neurons at each layer) remains a complex and challenging problem, as no universal methodology exists [55–57]. Excessive complexity may cause overfitting, while overly simple designs risk underfitting. To mitigate these issues, the early stopping technique was employed. This method uses a number of unseen cases, referred to as the validation set, to monitor the model performance and halt training when overfitting is detected, i.e., when validation error increases for several consecutive iterations.

The training-validation procedure of the ANN model in the present study follows the process outlined below. Let $L_{\text{train}}(\omega)$ and $L_{\text{val}}(\omega)$ represent the loss functions of the training and validation sets, respectively, where ω denotes the weights of the network. During training, the network iteratively updates its weights to minimize $L_{\text{train}}(\omega)$ using the LMA. After each training epoch (τ), the performance of the network is evaluated by computing $L_{\text{val}}(\omega_\tau)$. If $L_{\text{val}}(\omega_\tau)$ stops decreasing for a predefined number of consecutive epochs, referred to as validation checks, training is halted to prevent overfitting. As training progresses, the training loss $L_{\text{train}}(\omega_\tau)$ ideally decreases as the model learns from the data, with the goal of converging and completing the training process. The number of epochs must be selected to balance the training process, mitigating both overfitting and underfitting—where the network fails to capture the underlying patterns in the data.

2.2. Physical modelling

The WEC model used in the present study for physical modelling is an L-shaped OWC device scaled to 1:30, which has been used in previous studies [27] (Fig. 2). The model was scaled to properly account for air compressibility effects by ensuring that the ratio between the model and prototype air chamber volume was set according to [58]:

Fig. 2. Cross-section of the OWC model (1:30 scale, dimensions in mm).

$$\frac{V_p}{V_m} = k_p \delta \lambda^2, \quad (1)$$

where V represents the air chamber volume; k_p is the polytropic exponent of the turbine; λ is the scale factor; δ is the ratio of model to prototype water density; and the subscripts m and p denote the model and prototype, respectively. To meet this requirement, the additional air volume was provided by an air reservoir connected to the air chamber of the model. To accurately modelling free-surface flows [6], the wet part of the model was scaled to ensure that the Froude number remained consistent between model and prototype. Experimental tests were carried out at the University of Santiago de Compostela in its Hydraulic Laboratory, which is equipped with a wave flume measuring 20 m in length, 0.65 m in width, and 0.95 m in height. Waves were generated using a piston-type paddle incorporating an active absorption system to minimize wave re-reflections. The instrumentation included nine wave gauges distributed along the flume to record free surface elevations at various locations, two ultrasonic level sensors to track oscillations of the water column, and a differential pressure transducer to measure the pressure difference between the atmosphere and the interior of the chamber. Air pressure was monitored using a Druck-Unik5000 differential pressure transducer, with a measurement range of ± 3400 Pa and an accuracy of $\pm 0.04\%$ of full scale. The oscillations of the water column were recorded by means of two Honeywell 943-F4V ultrasonic level sensors, each with an accuracy of ± 1 mm. A comprehensive description of the experimental set-up is presented in [27].

The experimental campaign included 42 different irregular wave conditions, with significant wave heights reaching up to 5 m (operational limit of the converter) and wave energy periods ranging from 4 to 15 s [59] (Fig. 3), virtually representing the wave characteristics at any potential location of interest.

Due to the critical role of the turbine-chamber coupling [27], it is essential to accurately evaluate the performance of the chamber when operating with turbines of different characteristics. This requires reproducing the damping effect that each turbine induces on the oscillations of the water column, which was achieved through orifices of different diameters. This method, widely validated in previous studies [60], effectively emulates the turbine-induced damping caused by non-linear turbines, such as self-rectifying impulse turbines. Following previous works, the damping provided by each orifice was characterized by the dimensionless damping coefficient, defined as [27]:

$$B_c = \frac{\Delta p^{1/2}}{Q} \frac{A_c}{\rho_w^{1/2}}, \quad (2)$$

where Δp represents the pressure drop across the turbine, which drives fluid flow; Q corresponds to the volumetric flow rate of air passing

Fig. 3. Energy bins covered in the experimental campaign. The crosses indicate the representative irregular wave condition for each energy bin.

Table 1

Orifice diameters (d) and corresponding values of the turbine-induced damping (B_c) tested in physical model experiments. Orifices 1, 2, 3 and 5 were obtained from [27].

Orifice number	d (mm)	B_c
1	29	1.89
2	25	2.61
3	22	3.23
4	20	3.86
5	17	5.35
6	14	7.82
7	12	10.58

through the orifice; and A_c accounts for the plan area of the OWC device; finally, ρ_w stands for the density of the water.

During the present experimental campaign, three orifice diameters were tested: $d = 12, 14$ and 20 mm. Additionally, the dataset in [27] was incorporated, resulting in a total of seven values of the turbine-induced damping (Table 1). All of them were tested under the wave conditions indicated above. As a result, a final dataset of 294 test cases was obtained, providing an appropriate dataset for the ANN model and ensuring an extensive set of data cases for effective training and validation.

For each test (defined by a combination of significant wave height, wave energy period and a value of the turbine-induced damping), the capture-width ratio, defined as a measure of the efficiency of an OWC device [61,62], was calculated as:

$$C_{wr} = \frac{P_p}{P_w w_c}, \quad (3)$$

where w_c denotes the width of the air chamber in the direction parallel to the wave fronts; P_p is the pneumatic power captured by the OWC; and P_w is the incident mean wave power. The C_{wr} represents the proportion of the wave power intercepted by the width of the OWC chamber that is converted into pneumatic power.

The mean pneumatic power captured by the OWC converter was calculated using the following expression [63]:

$$P_p = \frac{1}{t_{max}} \int_0^{t_{max}} \Delta p Q dt, \quad (4)$$

where Δp represents the pressure drop; Q is the air flow rate; and t_{max} is the total duration of the test. The pressure drop was directly measured during the experimental campaign. The flow rate was calculated from the pressure drop using the pressure-vs-flow-rate ratios obtained through numerical modelling following the procedure described in [27].

The mean wave power for each test was computed as:

$$P_w = \rho_w g \int_0^{\infty} S(f) C_g(f) df, \quad (5)$$

where $S(f)$ is the spectral energy density obtained from incident-reflected wave analysis [64]; and $C_g(f)$ is the group velocity corresponding to each frequency band. This approach has been widely applied in previous studies to estimate the mean wave power, both for OWC devices (e.g., [15]) and for WECs in general (e.g., [65]).

2.3. Resource characterization

The performance of an OWC is site specific, which means that it depends on the wave conditions at a location of interest. To further assess the ANN model, its capability for predicting the OWC performance is analysed by considering real wave conditions of operation at a site of interest in the Galician Coast previously proposed for OWC operation ($X = 510281.79$ m, $Y = 4677697.00$ m; WGS84-UTM29N)

[66]. To this end, and with the aim of ensuring accuracy in the results, the site-specific characterization matrix is computed, providing the hours of occurrence and power, and thus the energy available, for the different combinations of energy bins, defined as intervals of significant wave heights (H_{m0}) and energy periods (T_e). The resulting characterization matrix is shown in Fig. 4. This matrix is obtained by applying the WEDGE methodology, combining a complex procedure of selection of wave conditions in deepwater, and their propagation towards the location of interest through spectral numerical modelling techniques. More specifically, the WEDGE methodology is applied through different stages. The first stage consists in characterizing and selecting the deepwater energy bins of interest at an offshore location where an extensive dataset of deepwater sea-state records is available. To this end, the deepwater resource is characterized by the probability of occurrence of trivariate energy bins, defined by intervals of H_{m0} , T_e , and mean direction (θ_m) with a specific resolution, along with their associated power (P) and energy. Then, the most energetic bins contributing to 95% of the total available energy are retained and propagated towards the coast through high-resolution spectral numerical modelling. As a result, a large amount of spatial information becomes available throughout the nearshore area of interest, consisting of the main spectral parameters (H_{m0} , T_e , θ_m , P) and the occurrence of a given number of wave cases. This information is used to reconstruct the 2D energy bins at the location of interest (closest grid node of the numerical grid), thereby resulting in a wave energy resource characterization matrix [59].

2.4. OWC-ANN model implementation

2.4.1. Data and preprocessing

The inputs of the ANN comprise the key variables influencing the performance of the OWC: the wave conditions, including H_{m0} and T_e , and the dimensionless damping coefficient (B_c), which represents the influence of the turbine on the OWC chamber. The MLP output is the capture-width ratio (C_{wr}), which is predicted for each combination of input variables. The ANN model can be mathematically defined as:

$$C_{wr} = f_{ANN}(H_s, T_e, B_c), \quad (6)$$

for the ANN model to identify the underlying relationships among the inputs, a corresponding set of target values, C_{wr} values in this case, has to be provided. These targets indicate to the network the expected output for each given combination of input variables, guiding the network in

Fig. 4. Resource characterization matrix at the coastal site of interest showing the annual hours of occurrence (numbers) and energy (colour code) provided by the different energy bins.

learning the correct relationships during training.

Prior to training the ANN, the input and target data were normalized to scale them within the range $[-1, 1]$. This normalization is a key step in enhancing the performance of neural networks as it improves convergence by ensuring that all variables contribute proportionally during training [67]. In this study, data normalization [68] was conducted according to the following expression:

$$Y_{normalized} = 2 \frac{Y - \min(Y)}{\max(Y) - \min(Y)} - 1, \quad (7)$$

where $Y_{normalized}$ represents a normalized data variable and Y an input data variable (unnormalized).

2.4.2. Network set-up

To determine the optimum ANN architecture for the specific task of predicting the capture-width ratio of the OWC, a comparative study was conducted. In particular, networks with one hidden layer were evaluated, varying the number of hidden neurons from 3 to 60. Each architecture was trained using the LMA backpropagation algorithm, as previously described. The details of the training-validation procedure are provided in the following section.

The activation function used for the neurons in the hidden layer was the hyperbolic tangent sigmoid, commonly referred to as *tansig*. This function is commonly employed to introduce non-linearity in neural networks [69], particularly in models that use hidden layers. In addition, the *tansig* function effectively maps all values within the normalization range $[-1, 1]$. The *tansig* function is defined as follows:

$$y = \frac{2}{1 + e^{-2x}} - 1. \quad (8)$$

where x represents an input variable and y the result of applying the *tansig* function. In the case of the output neuron, a linear transfer function is implemented:

$$y = x. \quad (9)$$

where x represents an input variable and y the result of applying the linear function.

Each network model was trained for a maximum of 750 epochs, as convergence was not achieved beyond this value, with validation checks set to 8 epochs to trigger early stopping. These parameters were selected based on empirical observations. Configurations that failed to converge within the specified epochs were retrained to minimize potential spurious results in the performance of the ANN architectures. During retraining, the weights of the ANN model are re-initialized by assigning new random values.

2.4.3. Training and cross-validation

The validation of the ANN model consists in checking its generalization capabilities by comparing the network outputs against the actual targets for previously unseen cases. The approach followed in this work applies the K -fold cross-validation technique [70], in which the dataset is divided into K equally sized subsets (folds). The ANN model is trained K times, using $K - 1$ subsets for training while reserving the subset left out for testing. The final accuracy of the ANN model is determined as the average performance of the K training-testing iterations. This technique ensures that the selection of the testing data is both representative and unbiased. Following previous works, the dataset was divided into 10 subsets ($K = 10$) [71]. Additionally, to apply the early stopping technique and prevent overfitting, the $K - 1$ subsets designated for training were further randomly divided into training and validation subsets, with 85% of the data allocated to training and 15% to validation. A scheme illustrating the data division is presented in Fig. 5.

From the complete initial dataset, which includes seven different orifices diameters, the data corresponding to one entire orifice were kept only for a final evaluation of the generalization capabilities of the ANN model. As a result, the training, validation and test dataset consists of 252 cases (a total of 294 cases considering all orifices). In each K iteration, 25 cases are used for testing, 193 for training and 34 for validation.

Finally, to mitigate the effects of the random initialization of weights and to thoroughly assess network performance across different initial conditions, each ANN model was trained 10 times ($N = 10$). Consequently, a total of 100 simulations ($K \times N$ combinations) were conducted per ANN architecture.

Fig. 5. Scheme of the 10-fold cross-validation technique applied to the ANN models. In each of the K iterations, the validation cases (black circles) are randomly selected from the data into the $K - 1$ subsets.

2.4.4. Performance parameters

The performance of each ANN model was evaluated by the root mean squared error (RMSE) and the correlation coefficient between predicted and actual (experimental) values [72]. The RMSE is defined as:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - y_i)^2}, \quad (10)$$

where x represents the values of the targets; y stands for the output values of the net.

The correlation coefficient (R) is defined as follows [73]:

$$R = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2 (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}, \quad (11)$$

where \bar{y} and \bar{x} corresponds with the average values of the output and target sets.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Physical model results

The capture-width ratio matrices obtained from the experimental testing campaign for the different values of the turbine-induced damping are displayed in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7. The matrices in Fig. 6 correspond to the results obtained in [27], while the second group of matrices in Fig. 7 represents the additional values of the turbine-induced damping specifically tested in the present study. Given that the highest efficiency in the previous campaign was achieved at the highest tested value of turbine-induced damping, the additional selected damping values to be tested were higher, ensuring a comprehensive characterization of the OWC performance across the full range damping values, both above and below the optimum level.

For each matrix in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, maximum efficiency is consistently achieved for energy periods within the range of 8–10 s. Notably, this efficiency range remains stable across the different turbine-induced

damping levels, indicating that the resonant frequency of an OWC chamber is largely unaffected by turbine-induced damping.

The comparison of the matrices highlights the substantial influence of turbine-induced damping on the performance of OWC systems. The capture-width ratio exhibits significant variations among energy bins, depending on the damping coefficient. Notably, the damping coefficient can be easily adjusted by selecting an appropriate turbine diameter, without affecting turbine performance [27]. The maximum capture-width ratio ($C_{wr} = 0.82$) was found for a dimensionless damping coefficient of $B_c = 7.82$, for the energy bin corresponding to significant wave heights in the range $0 \text{ m} < H_{m0} < 1 \text{ m}$ and energy periods between $8 \text{ s} < T_e < 9 \text{ s}$.

3.2. ANN model selection

3.2.1. Selection of ANN architecture

The performance of the different ANN architectures analysed is presented in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, by using the RMSE of the test subset as the quality control metric. Each architecture is identified using the format [inputs – hidden neurons – output neurons]. The selection of the model has been conducted in two steps. Firstly, the 58 trained models are displayed in a line chart (Fig. 8), where the area with the most favourable performance is delimited for subsequent precision analysis. Then, the dataset statistics are depicted through a box-and-whisker diagram (Fig. 9), in which boxes represent the interquartile range (IQR), encapsulating the middle 50% of RMSE values, with horizontal lines indicating the median of the set; whiskers illustrate the range of non-outlier RMSE values, defined as those within $1.5 \times \text{IQR}$ from the quartiles; finally, the notches represent the variability of the median between samples [74].

The behaviour of the model illustrates that the variation of RMSE sharply decreases at the beginning, reaching a stable area around 10 neurons in the hidden layer. Beyond this point, RMSE values fluctuate without a clear trend before exhibiting a gradual increase as the number of neurons continues to rise. The region between approximately 11 and 30 neurons presents the lowest RMSE values and is retained for further

Fig. 6. Capture-width ratio matrices of the OWC converter for the four values of the dimensionless damping coefficient experimentally tested in [27].

Fig. 7. Capture-width ratio matrices of the OWC converter for the three new values of the dimensionless damping coefficient experimentally tested in the present work.

Fig. 8. Performance of the different ANN architectures (N_e) of the test subset in terms of RMSE for the 58 trained models, ranging in values from 3 to 60 hidden neurons.

analysis.

From Fig. 9, it can be observed that, in general, the different ANN architectures (N_e) are accurate for predicting the capture-width ratio of the OWC converter, with median RMSE values below 0.03 for all the analysed architectures. As the number of neurons increases, the RMSE values fluctuate in both median magnitude and spread, making it impossible to establish any clear trend. The lowest median RMSE was

achieved for the [3-20-1] architecture, corresponding to 20 neurons in the hidden layer, yielding a median value of 0.0214. Additionally, this architecture exhibits a compact IQR and an absence of outliers, indicating reduced prediction errors and improved generalization capability compared to other configurations. Consequently, this architecture was selected. This selection procedure is consistent with previous works conducted under regular wave conditions, in which it has demonstrated reliable performance [27].

Once the ANN architecture was selected, the next step is to identify the optimum model among the 100 models trained within the 20-neuron architecture (ten models for each K iteration). The dataset statistics for the [3-20-1] architecture is illustrated through a box-and-whisker diagram in Fig. 10. Differences can be observed in both RMSE spread (IQR) and central tendency (median) across the K iterations. This variation suggests that the networks exhibit varying levels of predictive accuracy and consistency depending on the dataset used for training and validation. To ensure a proper network generalization, the selected model corresponds to K iteration with the lowest median of those without outliers: $K = 6$. Configurations such as $K = 3, 4, 8$ and 10 exhibit higher RMSE variability, as evidenced by the presence of outliers and larger IQRs. Other configurations, including $K = 2, 5,$ and 9 , demonstrate moderate performance with relatively stable RMSE values. However, their median RMSE values remain higher than the selected, indicating room for improvement. As a final step, among the $N = 10$ models trained for each K iteration, the model with the best performance was selected.

3.2.2. Performance of the selected ANN

In order to evaluate the performance of the selected ANN model, linear regression graphs comparing network outputs (C_{wr} estimates generated by the ANN) and target values (C_{wr} obtained from the experimental testing program) are presented in Fig. 11, Fig. 12 and

Fig. 9. Performance of the best ANN architectures (N_e) of the test subset in terms of RMSE. The boxes represent the interquartile range (IQR), with horizontal lines indicating the median of the set. Whiskers extend to show the range of non-outlier RMSE values. Circles denote outliers.

Fig. 10. Performance of the [3-20-1] architecture (test subset) in terms of RMSE. The boxes represent the interquartile range (IQR), with horizontal lines indicating the median of the set. Whiskers extend to show the range of non-outlier RMSE values. Circles denote outliers.

Fig. 13 for the training, validation and test sets, respectively. The performance of the ANN model on the training subset achieved a correlation coefficient of $R = 0.9989$, with all data points lying close to the $x = y$ line, and the best linear fit coincident with this line (Fig. 11) and given by the expression:

$$y = 0.9965x + 0.0014. \tag{12}$$

This result indicates an exceptionally accurate learning of the cases during the training process.

The validation subset comprises a percentage of the dataset set aside during the training process to prevent overfitting by evaluating the performance of the model against unseen data. The analysis presented in Fig. 12 demonstrates a correlation coefficient of $R = 0.9943$ for the validation subset, which is slightly lower than that of the training set.

Fig. 11. Linear regression for the training set. The targets represent the capture-width ratio obtained from the experimental testing program and the outputs the corresponding values estimated by the ANN.

Fig. 12. Linear regression for the validation set. The targets represent the capture-width ratio obtained from the experimental testing program and the outputs the corresponding values estimated by the ANN.

However, considering that the validation subset involves unseen data, the model exhibits a high degree of accuracy. In fact, a correlation coefficient higher than that of the training subset might indicate a biased selection of the validation cases or rote learning. The best linear fit expression obtained for this subset is:

$$y = 0.9892x + 0.0042. \tag{13}$$

Finally, the test set provides an evaluation of the actual performance

Fig. 13. Linear regression for the test set. The targets represent the capture-width ratio obtained from the experimental testing program and the outputs the corresponding values estimated by the ANN.

of the ANN model, as it consists of data reserved from the initial step and not introduced to the neural network during either training or validation. The linear regression graph in Fig. 13 reflects an excellent agreement between outputs and targets, with a correlation coefficient of $R = 0.9941$, nearly identical to that obtained for the validation subset. This consistency confirms that the network is not overfitted and performs reliably across unseen data. The best linear fit expression obtained for the test subset is given by:

$$y = 0.9635x + 0.0147. \tag{14}$$

By comparing the best-linear-fit line with the $x = y$ line, it can be seen that, in general, the ANN model tends to slightly underestimate mid to higher capture-width ratio values ($C_{wr} > 0.5$) while overestimating for mid to lower values ($C_{wr} < 0.5$). A similar trend can be discerned for the validation set (Fig. 12). For the most usual values of C_{wr} , ranging from approximately 0.2 to 0.6, the accuracy of the ANN model is even better than that previously indicated (whole range of values), showing in this range virtually perfect fit ($y = x$).

These results yield higher correlation coefficients than those reported for other AI-based approaches considering nested ANN [37,75], and achieve a performance comparable to higher computationally demanding methods, such as genetic algorithms [76], which are typically applied to more complex optimisation problems.

3.3. Application to efficiency matrix

To demonstrate the prediction capabilities of the ANN for estimating overall figures of capture-width ratio for a particular coastal location, it is also essential to evaluate its performance at the level of individual energy bins. Thus, the ANN model was used to predict the capture-width ratio matrix for the unseen value of the dimensionless damping coefficient ($B_c = 3.86$). Both the experimentally obtained and ANN predicted matrices are displayed in Fig. 14.

The comparison between the experimental data and the ANN predictions highlights the strong performance of the model, demonstrating its ability to accurately predict the capture-width ratio across the energy bins of the matrix. While the ANN prediction (Fig. 14-right) exhibits a

Fig. 14. Capture-width ratio matrices of the OWC converter for $B_c = 3.86$: experimental (left) and ANN predicted (right).

very slight underestimation, particularly around the central bins of the matrix ($8 \text{ s} < T_e < 10 \text{ s}$), it overall provides a highly accurate estimate of the energy distribution across the entire matrix. The comparison between the capture-width ratio values of both matrices yielded an overall RMSE of 0.021, with a correlation coefficient of $R = 0.9909$. This reinforces the reliability of the model in capturing the general capture-width ratio trends of this damping configuration. Furthermore, these results are in line with related works on power estimation and parameter optimisation of WECs [42,77].

3.4. Application to turbine damping selection

To fully validate the ANN model, it was used in a real application: determining the optimum turbine-induced damping for an OWC device operating at a particular coastal site of interest, based on its site specific wave resource as defined by its characterization matrix (Section 2.3). To this end, the ANN model was used to predict the capture-width ratio for

each energy bin in the characterization matrix across a wide range of values of the dimensionless damping coefficient, from $B_c = 1.4$ to 11. Using the capture-width ratio of each energy bin, the pneumatic energy captured for each bin was determined from the incident wave power and the occurrence of the corresponding sea states (Fig. 4). Then, the mean capture-width ratio for each damping level was calculated as the ratio of the total pneumatic energy (summed across all bins) to the total wave energy. These results are presented in Fig. 15. It should be noted that six values of the dimensionless damping coefficient ($B_c = 1.89, 2.61, 3.23, 5.35, 7.82$ and 10.58) were used for training and validating the ANN model, but a complete set of tests for an additional damping level ($B_c = 3.86$) was reserved for validating the performance of the model when facing new cases. The comparison between the experimental and ANN-predicted mean capture-width ratios yielded an overall RMSE of 0.002, while the absolute error for the unseen damping level was 0.004.

The ANN model demonstrates high accuracy across the data points corresponding to the values of the dimensionless damping coefficient

Fig. 15. Mean capture-width ratio values obtained by the ANN model (continuous line) for different values of the dimensionless damping coefficient. The circles indicate the actual values obtained from experimental modelling, being data used for training and validating the network. The asterisk represents an additional experimental value unseen by the network, intentionally reserved for validation purposes. The dashed line indicates the optimum damping.

used during training (circles in Fig. 15). These results demonstrate that the model can reliably predict the mean capture-width ratio for any damping condition, thereby enabling the identification of the overall best-performing dimensionless damping coefficient. For this particular coastal site, the optimum damping level—defined as the value yielding the highest mean capture-width ratio—is $B_c = 3.70$, enabling the model to capture 56.4% of the available wave energy at the selected location. Comparing the ANN prediction with the unseen damping, an excellent agreement is found. These results confirm the reliability of the ANN by achieving values closely aligned with the targets, further reinforcing the accuracy and robustness of the model. In contrast to the approach in [78], where damping optimisation was performed by scanning a finite set of orifice diameters in a wave flume, the ANN model provides continuous interpolation across damping values and sea states, significantly reducing the number of required physical model tests.

4. Conclusions

This study presents a novel methodology that integrates artificial neural networks (ANNs) with physical modelling to characterize the hydrodynamic performance of an L-shaped oscillating water column (OWC) device. The approach accounts for realistic operational conditions, including irregular waves and non-linear effects such as air compressibility. A multilayer perceptron feedforward neural network model was developed, trained, and validated using experimental data, enabling the detailed performance characterization of OWC devices in terms of the capture-width ratio under various configurations of incident wave conditions and turbine characteristics while relying on a limited number of physical model tests.

A 10-fold cross-validation procedure demonstrated the excellent capability of the neural network to address the proposed problem, achieving values of the root mean square error (RMSE) below 5% across virtually all 58 tested architectures. Among them, the [3-20-1] model—an architecture comprising 3 inputs, 20 hidden neurons and 1 output neuron—emerged as the optimum ANN configuration, yielding an RMSE below 2.5% and a correlation coefficient very close to unity ($R = 0.9941$). The selected ANN model demonstrated strong generalization capabilities in predicting both the mean capture-width ratio of the OWC device when operating at a given location under a range of values of the turbine-induced damping ($RMSE < 1\%$) and the capture-width ratio of individual energy bins (combinations of wave height and energy period) ($RMSE < 2.5\%$). In both cases, the model exhibited high accuracy, allowing for the evaluation of untested input configurations. As a practical application, the optimum damping for an OWC operating at a particular coastal site of interest was determined based on the performance predictions of the ANN model. For the selected case study on the Galician coast, an optimum value of the dimensionless damping coefficient of $B_c = 3.70$ was obtained, corresponding to a capture of 56.4% of the available wave energy resource.

In sum, the ANN model developed in the present study accurately predicts the performance of OWC devices operating under site-specific conditions. These capabilities enable a reduction in experimental efforts without compromising the reliability of the predictions, effectively complementing physical modelling and making the design and optimization process of OWC devices more accessible and cost-effective.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

B. Álvarez: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **D.M. Fouz:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Software, Investigation. **I. López:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation. **R. Carballo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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